

Multicomponent Spinels for Advanced Optical Technologies

Version 1

Description

Data management plan for the LCS project Sustainable Multicomponent Spinels for Advanced Optical Technologies: Modelling and Synthesis.

DFT and molecular dynamics simulated data.

Funder

Latvian Council of Science | | LCS

Grant

Izp-2025/1-0352

Researchers

Alexander Platonenko (0000-0002-8800-3411)

Organizations

Institute of Solid State Physic, University of Latvia

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [Multicomponent Spinels for Advanced Optical Technologies](#)

Description:

Data management plan for the LCS project Sustainable Multicomponent Spinels for Advanced Optical Technologies: Modelling and Synthesis.

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Researchers:

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Organizations:

[Institute of Solid State Physic, University of Latvia](#)

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: [Latvian Council of Science](#) | [LCS](#)

Grants: [lzp-2025/1-0352](#)

Project: [Cite Project](#)

3. License

License: [AFL-3.0](#)

Access Rights: [Public](#)

Publication Date: [2026-03-01](#)

4. Templates

[Descriptions](#)

[LCS FARP](#)

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Simulated structures and properties of multicomponent oxide spinels.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Experimental data
- Other

Simulated data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

TXT

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

50

GB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

No

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, request access (access is restricted, but request with collaboration proposal could be submitted to the authors)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

txt reader

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

Yes

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Academic Free License 3.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2026-12-31

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

No

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Alexander Platonenko (0000-0002-8800-3411)

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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